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Developing A Strategic Framework For Circular Economy In Urban Waste Management In Sokoto Metropolis

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Abstract: Sokoto state has a land area of 28,232. 37sq kilometres, Sokoto state has population of 3,696, 99 people and majority are Hausa Fulani. Over 80 percent of inhabitants practice one form of agriculture or the other. The rapid urbanization of Sokoto metropolis has led to significant environmental and health concerns due to inadequate waste management practices. This paper aims to develop a strategic framework for circular economy-based urban waste management in Sokoto Metropolis. Using a retrospective and prospective analysis, this study will investigate the current waste management practices, identify challenges and opportunities and explore international best practices in circular economy-based waste management. Informal waste recycling makes a great contribution to waste resource recovering, job provisioning and by extension, the sustainable urban development. It was found that, wastes are often burned or disposed of on landfills, open dumps and water bodies without prior treatment. Thus, waste management is a bottleneck in Sokoto because of weak or lack of enforcement of environmental regulatory policies and laws. This may be connected with challenges like inadequate environmental awareness, poor land-use, missing recycling, inadequate funding, and lack of technological innovations.

Keywords: circular economy; waste management; environmental health; waste recycling.

INTRODUCTION

The circular economy as a concept that is currently trending in the global research arena and it has garnered considerable attention among scholars as well as being adopted by institutions, policymakers, and other key economic sectors. This can be attributed to its uniqueness in articulating a restorative and regenerative approach to resource administration as opposed to the traditional linear model (Singh and Ordonez 2016). The concept focuses on the product and is commonly applied at the design, production, consumption and waste management stages. In the area of waste resource management, the existing solutions tend to view waste products as a nuisance that constitute negativities to the environment, natural resources and public health therefore, solutions have been proffered bearing this in mind (Ezeudu and Ezeudu 2019). Furthermore, in the linear economy model, solid waste handling modalities view waste products as a problematic commodity that often entails the deployment of scarce resources to manage them. In most developing countries, waste Recycling management is seen as an essential service to the citizenry and therefore, municipalities carve out a substantial part of their annual budget for solid waste management without projecting any significant return on the investment. Even when a public-private partnership is deployed, the aim is often to maximize revenue collection from the public to ensure effective waste management services such as collection, transportation, and disposal. However, the circular economy model promotes the concept that a product that has been perceived to have reached its

end-of-life in a particular system might be used as a raw material in another or the same system (Ellen MacArthur 2022). The circularity principle further reframes the traditional viewpoint by considering waste products as resources that could have an endless or multiple lifespans, with economic, social and environmental gains. It has been established by researchers that poor solid waste management is one of the major problems confronting Sokoto state with no remarkable headway by the government in solving the problem (Amusan, 2018-2023; Anekwe, 2016). A major milestone in solid waste management in Nigeria came with the establishment of the Federal Environmental Protection Agency (FEPA) in 1988. The FEPA was later merged with other key government agencies to form the Federal Ministry of Environment in 1999. The responsibility of this ministry is to issue guidelines on how key environmental issues, including solid waste management, should be tackled. However, the task of making laws, implementations and enforcement mostly lie on the state governments through various state ministries of the environment and municipal councils.

The guideline on solid waste management in the country was released in 2005 by the Federal Ministry of Environment. The policy document recognized the fact that strategies for waste management at the grassroots level should interface with the local culture, land use type, economic base, climatic condition, existing urbanization level and institutional arrangements Sokoto Environmental Protection Agency (SEPA) was mandated to collect and transport commercial and industrial waste to designated landfill sites as well as manages the landfills. In 1997, Private Sector Participation (PSP) scheme was introduced to complement the efforts of SEPA. The participants were assigned the responsibility of door to door / bulk waste collection in Sokoto metropolis alone at fees to be paid by serviced clients. This tripling generation of waste management may not be unconnected with some noticeable economic and social progress linked with urbanization and population growth (Hoornweg, et.al., 2012). Also, waste collection service is offered mainly by the public sector though SEPA but Governments grant license to 11 private waste disposal companies for effective refuse collection in the metropolis. It is not, however, uncommon to see informal waste collector using local vehicles (push carts) for collection services from door to door in some parts of Sokoto metropolis.

The World Bank report shows that:

- 3.5 billion people, or half of the world's population, are without access to waste management services, and open dumping remains the prevalent waste-disposal method in most low- and lower-middle-income countries.
- More than 1.3 billion tonnes of municipal solid waste were estimated to have been generated in 2012, and 2.2 billion tonnes a year are expected by 2025.
- Urbanisation, industrialisation, increasing population, and economic development contribute to the rise in waste and its increasing complexity and hazardousness.

The Sustainable Development Goals of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development adopted by the world leaders in 2015 include proper waste management and a strategic vision for using waste as resources in a more circular economy. All countries of the UN-ECE region are making progress in this direction at different levels of economic development.

Literature Review

Today, more people are living in urban cities around the globe, generating about 1.3 billion tonnes of waste per annum at the rate of 1.2 kg/capita/day. Projections have it that by 2025, about 4.3 billion people will be residing in the world's urban areas generating 2.2 billion tons of solid waste per annum. The global costs of managing this waste will also rise from the current annual figure of \$205.4 billion to \$374.5 billion by 2025. In low and middle-income countries, the cost of waste collection is about 80–90% of the municipality's waste management annual budgets, yet the services are far from being efficient and often limited to visibility areas. Many cities throughout the world are worried about innovative infrastructure built on a circular economy. This need is mostly caused by a shortage of raw materials, an increase in the amount of hazardous waste, the expansion of unplanned landfills, and a dearth of energy

sources. In most cities, trash management has recently grown to be a top priority (Saha et al.,2021). The employment of an integrated approach in the Metropolitan waste management sector in each Nigerian state could be an effective way to surmount inherent challenges in the system. Such an approach would entail the strategic management of waste management through coordinated development and administration of a blend of new systems as well as a significant improvement of current ones, all within a contemporary framework (Christie, 2018). The mass burning method of waste disposal is commonly practised among residents of Sokoto metropolis and other cities in Nigeria (Ituen et al., 2019). For the sake of convenience, some residents prefer to set fire to their waste rather than walk a few miles to the communal collection points. The amount of items disposed of as municipal solid waste (MSW) has greatly increased as a result of population growth, urbanization, economic expansion, and related consumption habits. Large amounts of solid waste are currently being disposed of in Management Of Wastes For Attainment Of Circular Economy In Sokoto state, informal or official but uncontrolled dumpsites, endangering the environment and the health of the general people (UN-HABITAT, 2010; UNEP,2009; Kazuva and Zhang, 2019). Nigeria is yet to venture intensively into this resourceful environmental bioremediation through biodiversity. Thus, inefficient waste management is posing a terrible threat to this society (Ituen et al., 2009).

The UN has stated that “there are about 12 million hectares of farmland a year get seriously degraded” from many factors. After waste is disposed of in a landfill it starts to decompose. Global waste management Frameworks And Approaches Due to its significant role in providing a safe environment and addressing public health concerns associated with waste generation, solid waste management is considered an essential component of modern infrastructure in any society. The design of solid waste management systems should consider and encourage the reduction of waste, recycling and recovery of waste, utilization of appropriate waste treatment methods and more environmentally friendly technology as well as appropriate final disposal (Kofoworola, 2020). Solid waste management has over time evolved and improved to its current state in most developed countries; with these changes have come also the development of concurrent legislative requirements. As such, most have come up with contemporary national strategies for sustainable and efficient waste management; as a premier attempt at ameliorating solid waste disposal in the country, the United States developed the 1965 Solid Waste Disposal Act. This was amended under the Resource Conservation and Recovery Act. The latter represented how the country dealt with issues related to the disposal of solid waste; although revised to meet present requirements, it also serves as the avenue through which a framework for environmentally friendly solid waste management (including SWM) is developed via federal and states programs in the country. In Sokoto SEPA has promulgated policies and frameworks to combating the challenge of managing solid waste management to improve on the other waste system. In Nigeria several acts have come into existence; all having a common goal of environmental protection and amelioration, although with different concepts and strategies. It effectively underlined pollution containment from waste, and pollution avoidance which underlined avoidance of waste, re-use.

Waste as a Concept

Waste in the practical sense, is all the ordinary stuff that is thrown out from households or businesses, such as plastic, glass, food waste etc. They are categorized as “Municipal Solid Waste (MSW)” .Solid waste management encompasses the management of all types of waste materials, such as town waste, construction waste, industrial waste and agricultural waste. It is very important because improper collection of waste can lead to environmental depletion and health hazards. Effective and efficient solid waste management is crucial for the maintenance of good clean environment and it helps in prevention of diseases, reduces the risk of contamination of water, air and soil.

Circular Economy

With a continual increase in economic activity, economists and businesspeople have started to get concerned regarding the scarcity of raw materials, thus, creating ideas of an economy that differs from the traditional one. This new concept is mostly concerned with environmental sustainability, taking into

consideration future generations, and the well-being of the global citizen while utilizing products as much as they can and limiting the quantity of waste in the world. According to the Ellen Macarthur Foundation, “A circular economy is based on the principles of designing out waste and pollution, keeping products and materials in use, and regenerating natural systems” (What is the circular economy? The new economy would involve the line of production change from the traditional linear supply chain to a circular supply chain (Robinson, 2016). The supply chain has a huge impact on the overall waste problem in the global society, which is why huge importance is given to this aspect of the circular economy. The circular model seen in Figure 1 shows how after consumption and use, products move to recovery which then moves to the next stage where they are recycled and used as raw material.

Method of Waste Collection in Sokoto Metropolis

Methods of solid waste collection there are different modes, methods for solid waste collection system in Sokoto metropolis. The following are some of the methods that have been identified or obtained from this paper. Door to door collection; some residents had opted the use of door to door method. This is done by private collectors groups or organization in Sokoto metropolis though efficiency and effectiveness of this method is not much effective due to the reasons that individual or owners of the houses they do not contribute the small amount of money that they are supposed to contribute. Collection is sometimes done by small community groups which pass house to house, though community participation is poor, most of the solid waste households are disposed to the rivers and gullies Roadside collection. Some residents also used collection points which are located near the road. Streets which are not planned or no municipal vehicle access are supposed to collect their waste from their households and dump at secondary collection points where the (SEPA) vehicle can pass and load the waste ready to be transported to the main dumping areas located at the outskirts of the town. The main challenge is the performance of the (SEPA) vehicle and quantities of the waste produced, this cause most of wastes to be a burning issue to negative environmental effects, cause nuisance to people by emanating foul smell. Quite a number of people used communal container systems. The system have been in place in many years and are very help full in waste management processes by keeping the environment and Sokoto city clean. Communal bins are introduced to help those people, in flats and bedsits who don't have enough space to store their waste, over a week, 24 hours a day, and 7 days a week. The paper revealed that in most areas there's no communal bins placed to keep the waste. Most of the areas in Sokoto metropolis have no communal bins for keeping waste. It is believed that extending the coverage of communal containers is the best way of ensuring various streets to stay clean. If the municipal can place more bins, most of the households will no longer need to store their waste inside their property or outside their front door until collection day or brave the basement bin store. Instead they will be able to put their rubbish into the communal bin whenever it's convenient for them. The containers must be emptied regularly to prevent them from overflowing and ensure safe and healthier environment.

Curb-side collection is today often referred to as a strategy of local authorities to collect recyclable items from the consumer. Curb-side collection is considered a low-risk strategy to reduce waste volumes and increase recycling rates. Materials are typically collected in large bins, coloured bags, or small open plastic tubs, specifically designated for content. Curb-side collection is commonly considered to be completely environmentally friendly.

Economic Advantage of Waste disposal in Sokoto State

- Recycling recovery can generate revenue to the government from the sale of recovered refuse. Various valuable materials like plastics, metals, can be recovered and sold to manufacturing industries
- Job creation the state government can create numerous jobs in collection, recycling and waste materials. By investing in waste management Sokoto state can generate employment, improve local economy and supporting sustainable development.

- Cost saving effective and efficient waste management can lead to lower waste disposal costs for the government and private sector organization.
- Health and social benefits, it plays a vital role in improving public health and maintenance of overall quality of life of the people.
- By full implementation of effective and efficient waste management, we can reduce environmental pollution, conservation of natural resources and mitigate climate change.

Problems of Waste Management in Sokoto State

Solid waste management anywhere in the world is a problem that continually accelerates as a product of industrialization and population growth. As cities grow economically, greater business activity and diverse consumption patterns serve to drive up the solid waste quantities, Sokoto state has been principal victim of this disaster. Enough attention has been given to this challenge, but it seems to be a mere lip service that is played. A holistic and technical approach is needed since solid waste management is a complex challenge for the environment. (Schubeler 1996). Wastes that are not properly managed are a serious health hazards leading to the spread of infectious diseases. Unattended waste lying in the metropolis attracts dangerous creatures, rats and flies that in turn spread diseases. WHO (2024) estimates that globally there are nearly 1.7 billion cases of diarrhoeal disease every year about 1.8 million people die annually from diarrheal diseases where 90% are children under five to nine years, mostly in developing countries. With the increasing influx of the people and the rapid urbanization, huge amount of human and small scale business waste of about 950 tones generate out of which 480 tones are collected representing 51%. This leaves a substantial amount of back log that creates various kinds of inconveniences including health hazards to the people of Sokoto metropolis. Indiscriminate dumping of waste, irregular collection of waste generated and inadequate resources are the problems facing solid waste management in Sokoto metropolis. Also lack of equipment and the absence of proper engineered final disposal sites delay the emptying of containers placed at vantage points. These containers overflow and litter scattered around it leading to the possible factors of diarrheal diseases. It therefore becomes necessary for this study to develop a strategic framework for circular economy-based urban waste management in Sokoto Metropolis, focusing on the period 2015- 2025.

Health problems due to waste disposal

Records from many Hospitals in the state capital and neighbouring villages shows that aside diet, most of the reported cases of diseases are sanitation related of which solid waste is inclusive. Diseases such as malaria, cholera, typhoid fever and diarrheal diseases are commonly found in Sokoto metropolis. Human resources could be lost through poor waste management and this can affect productivity in the area. Solid waste management seems to be neglected and as such prompted the researcher to study circular economy-based urban waste management challenges and opportunities in Sokoto metropolis. The study therefore intends to explore appropriate strategies and policy recommendations in clearing urban waste in the sustainable manner.

CONCLUSION

Sustainable waste management is considered an essential component of modern infrastructure in society and also, encourages the reduction of waste, recycling and recovery of waste, utilization of appropriate waste treatment methods and more environmentally friendly technology as well as appropriate final disposal. To address the problem of global waste and stop the generation of trash from rising, effective waste management and governance are needed. Because plastics, iron, glasses, and cans are bad for the environment, circularity should be used to decrease their production. This papers will enhance the environmental awareness of waste management, household disposal of waste, and wastewater disposal. Sokoto metropolis was once referred to as the "cleanest city" due to its cleanliness and the abundance of plants and cleaners that were seen across the metropolis. However, Sokoto may currently be considered to be among the "garbage city" due to the numerous mountains of trash that litter the entire city. According

to studies, the Sokoto Metropolis produces between 700 and 1000 metric tons of refuse daily. The paper will recommend the introduction of household-based and industrial waste management schemes involving them in proper waste storage, collection, segregation, and recycling activities. One method that creates opportunity is the circular economy, which encourages the reuse of materials and lowers production and consumer waste. Improper management of waste and pollution in major cities contributes to environmental degradation, public health issues and frightening environmental problems in the world.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Sokoto state government should give total support to SEPA to carry out its functions without any undue influence. These include adequate funding and provision of vehicles and try-circles for evacuation of refuse.

There's the need for adequate collaboration in supporting the government by the international donor agencies in order to promote financial sustainability and accountability in service provision.

There must be effective sensitization of people in order not to be living in an unclean environment. The dangers involved and risks must be well communicated to the people.

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